

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Section 3.3.1.5: Changes in landscape-seascape disturbance regimes (intensification and reduction)

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Description

Section 3.3.1.5 assesses the role of changes in landscape-seascape disturbance regimes (intensification and reduction) as drivers of biological invasions. The experts conducted a systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on this driver. This systematic review consists in the main source of evidence for the section.

Process overview

Search 1:

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review

- **Search language(s):** English

- **Search terms:**

Search1: TITLE: ((invasibility OR "invasive alien species" OR "invasive species" OR "bio* invasion" OR invasion* OR "alien species" OR "non-native species" OR IASs OR "introduced species" OR "introduced plant*" OR "introduced animal*" OR "alien plant*" OR "alien pest*" OR "alien animal*" OR "invasive plant*" OR "invasive animal*" OR "invasion debt" OR "plant invas*" OR "animal invas*" OR "invas* risk" OR "invader*" OR "exotic species" OR "exotic plant*" OR "exotic animal*" OR "novel species")) AND TITLE: (("land use " OR "land-use" OR sea OR land OR habitat* OR cultivat* OR agricult* OR horticult* OR aquacult* OR fish*)) AND TOPIC: ((shift* OR change OR intensification OR intensity OR degrad* OR alterat* OR abandon* OR grazing OR fire OR fishing OR harvest* OR trawl* OR manag* OR control*))

Search 2: For general drivers within terrestrial systems:

Drivers disturbance invasive alien species \ plants \ animals "land use", "land change"

For general drivers within marine and freshwater systems:

Drivers disturbance invasive alien marine species \ freshwater \ oceanic \ aquatic

For fire related disturbances:

Fire management practices invasive alien species disturbance

For agricultural practices:

Agriculture, forestry, horticulture, invasive alien species disturbance

For microbial invasive species:

Microbial, invasive alien species, land use change, disturbance

- **Search engine:**

Search 1: Web of Science

Search 2: Google scholar

- **Date:** June 2020

- **Overview of the search results and selection criteria:**

Number of search result:

53 in total: 32 from Search 1, and 21 from Search 2

Selection criteria:

Search 1: Searched with above terms, then refined by DOCUMENT TYPES: (REVIEW) and Timespan: All years. Indexes: SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI, A&HCI, ESCI

Search 2: Searched with above terms, then Timespan.

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations): 0

- **Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.):**

Number of papers reviewed: 53 (See Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx)

Fields extracted:

- Publication title

- Year of publication

- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]

- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]

- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]

- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]

- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]

- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]

-Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life

-Comment (free text)

- **Files (code, review templates, etc.):**

Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx